

ISSUES OF GEOGRAPHICAL ASSESSMENT AND MONITORING OF
LAKES OF KHOREZM REGION

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Bekmetova Shoiram Hamid qizi

Urgench State University, master's student

Bekchanova Soxiba

Teacher of school No. 24 in Gurlan district of Khorezm region

Abdullayeva Maftuna Rashidovna

Teacher of school No. 6 in Gurlan district of Khorezm region

Annotation: *The article analyzes the problems of lakes and their geographical description, the current state of the lakes of Khorezm region as a result of geographical assessment and observation, the effective use of lakes and for what purposes they can be used.*

Keywords: *lake, mountain lake, plain lake, fresh water, salt water*

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Lakes with unique nature have been formed in each of the warm, temperate and cold climate zones around the globe. Exploring the lakes is very important. Because lakes are very important for the area, which is located as a natural object. The lakes are used for various purposes. In particular, it is used in fisheries, water supply, water transport, irrigation, for the production of mineral salts and medicinal muds. Lakes are also a potential source of clean fresh and very fresh water. By definition, a lake is a natural body of water collected in deep places (Baratov, 1991). The lakes are a place for fish, birds and various animal species, the flora that is suitable for this area and formed in the area.

There are sernam, arid regions on the surface. The relief features of the earth are also different. Accordingly, the lakes are divided into species. For example, depending on the appearance, whether the water flows out or not, depending on the temperature (temperature), depending on the salinity.

Lakes in the territory of Uzbekistan are divided into two types: 1. mountain lakes; 2. plain lakes. (Vahobov, 2005). Khorezm lakes belong to the category of plain lakes. Scientific work on the number of lakes and their characteristics is ongoing,

but there are many unregistered, unexplored lakes. It is very important to study them and use them wisely and effectively.

The number of man-made lakes in Khorezm region, especially in Uzbekistan, has been growing in recent years. These types of lakes are formed as a result of the discharge of drainage water from arable lands into natural pits outside the cultivated area. Some lake areas have been drained and turned mainly into rice fields. As a result, their area was reduced by 4-5 times. Most of the lakes are farmed by farms specializing in fishing and poultry.

Lakes have an active impact on the state of nature. They play an important role in the management of surface water flow. For example, it is a source of water accumulation during wet periods of the year. Lake water can be used during drought. Minerals and organic matter can accumulate as a result of runoff from groundwater and surface water. The physical and chemical properties of lake water, in turn, have a significant impact on life activities, determining the conditions for the development of aquatic animals and plant organisms.

The share of fresh water on Earth is only 2.5%, of which only 1% can be used. Therefore, lakes are one of the most important water resources, a source of water supply for human consumption and, in general, account for about 0.3% of the total sources of surface water bodies. The condition of the lakes has been steadily deteriorating due to the increasing anthropogenic activity that surrounds them. The quality of lake water is assessed using different physicochemical and biological parameters for different purposes. In general, natural lakes are limited water bodies that do not have a strong flow for self-purification of water. That is why different mixtures accumulate in the lake. By identifying the current characteristics of the lakes and analyzing the pollutants, it is possible to predict the future condition of the lake and determine the quality of the lake water. Various modeling methods are used to predict changes in lake water quality, such as water basin models, groundwater models, and lake models. The growing population is causing problems related to the intensification of urbanization and modernization processes, the construction of sewers and roads, the pollution of groundwater and surface water. Natural water is polluted as a result of rock breakage, soil washing and deposit processing, and so on. Water quality temperature, electrical conductivity, nitrate, phosphorus, potassium, can be evaluated by various parameters such as dissolved oxygen and so on. For example, the increase or decrease of a particular substance in lakes can affect the ecosystem of that area. Nitrogen and phosphorus accumulate in algae when there is an excess of nitrogen and phosphorus in the lake, which is in excess for lake conditions. As a result, algae grow rapidly, changing the aquatic ecosystem. Increased and overgrown algae

produce toxins, oxygen levels decrease. This can damage or kill the fish and create bad conditions for them to rest. Pollution of lakes with nitrogen and phosphorus is called nutrient pollution. This is due to wastewater treatment systems and some agricultural practices. Streets, asphalt roads, sewers, houses and buildings - these are all waterproof surfaces. They do not allow water to evaporate and come to the surface. The flow of water is accelerating, and water containing heavy metals, sediments, and pollutants flows into ditches and lakes. It is necessary to plant trees around the roads, propagate trees and plants around the canopy and ensure that water is absorbed into the soil and plants.

Lakes are inland bodies of water that do not have a direct exchange with the ocean. Because the boundaries between water and land, water and air are clear, there is a strong connection between many ecosystem components. Some lakes are saline due to evaporation or ingress of groundwater. Although lakes contain 50.01% of all surface water, they contain 49.8% of liquid surface fresh water.

Many “goods and services” such as fishing, agricultural irrigation, industrial activities and recreation are often dependent on lakes. As for the lakes of Khorezm region, it is scientifically based that there are currently 18,000 lakes, including very small lakes (Matchanov, 2020). As of the current state of the lakes, no concrete work has been done on monitoring the lakes. As the groundwater of the Khorezm region is close to the surface, lakes are formed in man-made depths. Currently, lakes and existing reservoirs are being monitored and analyzed on the basis of satellite data. The loss of lakes leads to an imbalance in nature, and groundwater levels rise and the process of salinization of lands intensifies.

Kaltakul, Kulonchikol, Otakul, Shurkul, Kokkol, Tukaykul, Ulugshurkul, Hajjali lake, Kepak, Uzunkul, Kurvankol Ozorniy, Karakul, Rovotkol in the region, Rovulkol, Dovdon, Davudkul, Obilkol, Tangali, Boyotkul, Kozikol, Kichik lake, Kurakkol and other similar small lakes. Especially Yangiariq district is the leader in the number of lakes in the region. Fishing is also well developed in the district. Khorezm fishery was formed in Yangiarik district. Measures are being taken to develop fishing in the lakes of Khorezm region. In conclusion, we can say that the importance of lakes is very important for man and nature. Its proper use is an important resource for human health, which in turn is important for the economy.

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